

A Winding Journey In The Nomenclature Of Odontogenic Keratocyst and a Revisit of the Four Editions Of The WHO Classification On Odontogenic Cyst And Tumours

Research Article

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Abstract

The Odontogenic Keratocyst has been a controversial odontogenic developmental cyst that has seen changes in terminology ever since its first description. The change in its terminology from being a simple cyst to a benign tumour was much debated when WHO rechristened it to Keratocystic Odontogenic Tumour in 2005. The widespread debate on this issue led to reverting the name back to Odontogenic Keratocyst by WHO in 2017. This article reviews the changes in its nomenclature and discusses the reasons that led to these changes. The article also includes all the four WHO classifications of Odontogenic lesions from 1971 to 2017 so that the reader may at a glance be able to summarize how the classification has evolved and changed over the last four decades.

Keywords: Odontogenic Keratocyst; Keratocystic Odontogenic Tumour; Who Classification Of Odontogenic Cysts And Tumours.

Introduction

It has been more than nine decades since the first description of this cyst and even today it remains the center of discussion among pathologists and surgeons worldwide and not only so established bodies like the WHO too have contributed significantly in understanding the journey in search of its true name and nature. The prologue must have definitely fired neurons in the minds of every reader, who immediately realizes this odyssey could only be about the legendary "Odontogenic Keratocyst". The present review article is an attempt at understanding this journey from its first description in 1940's till the recent change in terminology in the 2017 and all the names it acquired during its long winding journey.

The earlier terminologies and understanding the basic nature of the cyst

In the earliest literature the cyst was described as Cholesteatomatous by Hauer in 1926.^[1] This was followed on March 18, 1944, by Robinson, who presented a paper at the 22nd General Meeting of

the International Association for Dental Research in Chicago in which he described a classification that divided odontogenic cysts into periodontal cysts, dentigerous cysts, and primordial cysts. He used the term "Primordial cyst" for those cysts he believed that had a primordial origin and that this developed from remnants of the dental lamina or the enamel organs before enamel formation had taken place.^[2]

Philipsen in 1956, while still a senior dental student working with Jens J Pindborg in Copenhagen, named and described this cyst as "Odontogenic keratocyst."^[3] However the terms "Primordial cyst" and "Odontogenic Keratocyst" were used synonymously in the first edition (1971) and second edition (1992) of the WHO classification (Table 1 and 2), though the term Odontogenic Keratocyst was endorsed as more appropriate for this distinctive cystic lesion.^[4, 5]

While the discussion on the origin and terminology still continued, researchers working on OKCs could put all the pieces of the jigsaw together. They proposed that this cyst had a possible origin from undifferentiated dental lamina that these cysts had

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keratinized linings (predominantly parakeratin) and they showed a somewhat higher recurrence rate than other dental cysts. [6] Browne examined the relationship between these cyst and the crowns of the teeth and found that, although they were often related to the crown of a tooth, they were not truly dentigerous because they did not seem to have been derived from the reduced enamel organ and were not attached to the tooth at the cementoenamel junction. Browne recommended that the term “primordial cyst” be eliminated in favour of the neutral term “odontogenic keratocyst” because this name dealt with its histologic features

and not the origin, that defined its clinical behavior and higher recurrence rate.[7-9]

Journey from being a simple cyst to a benign tumour

The typical histologic features of the OKC include an epithelial lining of parakeratinized stratified squamous epithelium that is thin, about six to ten cells thick, lacks rete ridges, producing a flat epithelial connective tissue interface that often shows separation. Parakeratinized areas show surface corrugation. A well- defined

Table 1. WHO Histological Typing of Odontogenic Tumours, Jaw Cysts and Allied Lesions, First Edition, 1971. [5]

I. Neoplasms and other tumours related to the odontogenic apparatus

A. Benign

1. Ameloblastoma
2. Calcifying epithelial odontogenic tumour
3. Ameloblastic fibroma
4. Adenomatoid odontogenic tumor (adeno- ameloblastoma)
5. Calcifying odontogenic cyst
6. Dentinoma
7. Ameloblastic fibro-odontoma
8. Odonto-ameloblastoma
9. Complex odontoma
10. Compound odontoma
11. Fibroma (odontogenic fibroma)
12. Myxoma (myxofibroma)
13. Cementomas
 - a) Benign cementoblastoma (true cementoma)
 - b) Cementifying fibroma
 - c) Periapical cemental dysplasia (Periapical fibrous dysplasia)
 - d) Gigantiform cementoma (familial multiple cementomas)
14. Melanotic neuro-ectodermal tumour of infancy (melanotic progenoma, melano-ameloblastoma)

B. Malignant

1. Odontogenic carcinomas

- a. Malignant ameloblastoma
- b. Primary intra-osseous carcinoma
- c. Other carcinomas arising from odontogenic epithelium, including those arising from odontogenic cysts

2. Odontogenic sarcomas

- a. Ameloblastic fibrosarcoma (ameloblastic sarcoma)
- b. Ameloblastic odontosarcoma

II. Neoplasms and other tumours related to bone

A. Osteogenic neoplasms

1. Ossifying fibroma (fibro-osteoma)

B. Non-neoplastic bone lesions

1. Fibrous dysplasia
2. Cherubism
3. Central giant cell granuloma (giant cell reparative granuloma)
4. Aneurysmal bone cyst
5. Simple bone cyst (traumatic, haemorrhagic bone cyst)

III. Epithelial cysts

A. Developmental

1. Odontogenic

- a. Primordial cyst (keratocyst)
- b. Gingival cyst
- c. Eruption cyst
- d. Dentigerous (follicular) cyst

2. Non-odontogenic

- a. Naso-palatine duct (incisive canal) cyst
- b. Globulo-maxillary cyst
- c. Naso-labial (naso-alveolar) cyst

B. Inflammatory

1. Radicular cyst

IV. Unclassified lesions

Table 2- WHO Histological Typing of Odontogenic Tumours, From the Second Edition, 1992. 5

<p>1 Neoplasms and other tumours related to the odontogenic apparatus</p> <p>1.1 Benign</p> <p>1.1.1 Odontogenic epithelium without odontogenicectomesenchyme</p> <p>1.1.1.1 Ameloblastoma</p> <p>1.1.1.2 Squamous odontogenic tumour</p> <p>1.1.1.3 Calcifying epithelial odontogenic tumour (Pindborg tumour)</p> <p>1.1.1.4 Clear cell odontogenic tumour</p> <p>1.1.2 Odontogenic epithelium with odontogenicectomesenchyme, with or without dental hard tissue formation</p> <p>1.1.2.1 Ameloblastic fibroma</p> <p>1.1.2.2 Ameloblastic fibrodentinoma (dentinoma) and ameloblastic fibro-odontoma</p> <p>1.1.2.3 Odontoameloblastoma</p> <p>1.1.2.4 Adenomatoid odontogenic tumour</p> <p>1.1.2.5 Calcifying odontogenic cyst</p> <p>1.1.2.6 Complex odontoma</p> <p>1.1.2.7 Compound odontoma</p> <p>1.1.3 Odontogenic ectomesenchyme with or without included odontogenic epithelium</p> <p>1.1.3.1 Odontogenic fibroma</p> <p>1.1.3.2 Myxoma (odontogenic myxoma, myxofibroma)</p> <p>1.1.3.3 Benign cementoblastoma (cementoblastoma, true cementoma)</p> <p>1.2 Malignant</p> <p>1.2.1 Odontogenic carcinomas</p> <p>1.2.1.1 Malignant ameloblastoma</p> <p>1.2.1.2 Primary intraosseous carcinoma</p> <p>1.2.1.3 Malignant variants of other odontogenic epithelial tumours</p> <p>1.2.1.4 Malignant changes in odontogenic cysts</p> <p>1.2.2 Odontogenic sarcomas</p> <p>1.2.2.1 Ameloblastic fibrosarcoma (ameloblastic sarcoma)</p> <p>1.2.2.2 Ameloblastic fibrodentinosa sarcoma and ameloblastic fibro-odontosarcoma</p> <p>1.2.2 Odontogenic carcinosarcoma</p> <p>2 Neoplasms and other lesions related to bone</p> <p>2.1 Osteogenic neoplasms</p> <p>2.1.1 Cemento-ossifying fibroma (cementifying fibroma, ossifying fibroma)</p> <p>2.2 Non-neoplastic bone lesions</p> <p>2.2.1 Fibrous dysplasia of the jaws</p> <p>2.2.2 Cemento-osseous dysplasias</p> <p>2.2.2.1 Periapical cemental dysplasia (periapical fibrous dysplasia)</p> <p>2.2.2.2 Florid cemento-osseous dysplasia (gigantiform cementoma, familial multiple cementomas)</p> <p>2.2.2.3 Other cemento-osseous dysplasias</p> <p>2.2.3 Cherubism (familial multilocular cystic disease of the jaws)</p> <p>2.2.4 Central giant cell granuloma</p> <p>2.2.5 Aneurysmal bone cyst</p> <p>2.2.6 Solitary bone cyst (traumatic, simple, haemorrhagic bone cyst)</p> <p>2.3 Other tumours</p> <p>2.3.1 Melanotic neuroectodermal tumour of infancy (melanotic progonoma)</p> <p>3 Epithelial cysts</p> <p>3.1 Developmental</p> <p>3.1.1 Odontogenic</p> <p>3.1.1.1 "Gingival cyst" of infants (Epstein pearls)</p> <p>3.1.1.2 Odontogenic keratocyst (primordial cyst)</p> <p>3.1.1.3 Dentigerous (follicular) cyst</p> <p>3.1.1.4 Eruption cyst</p> <p>3.1.1.5 Lateral periodontal cyst</p> <p>3.1.1.6 Gingival cyst in adults</p> <p>3.1.1.7 Glandular odontogenic cyst; sialo-odontogenic cyst</p> <p>3.1.2 Nonodontogenic</p> <p>3.1.2.1 Nasopalatine duct (incisive canal) cyst</p> <p>3.1.2.2 Nasolabial (nasolabial) cyst</p>

basal layer composed of columnar or cuboidal cells showing hyperchromatic palisaded nuclei resembling a picket fence or a tomb stone appearance is noticed. Small "daughter" or "satellite" cysts may be present in the connective tissue wall of the cyst. Those cysts that had an orthokeratinized lining were separated from this category and called Orthokeratinized Odontogenic Cyst (OOC)

based on their histology and different biological behaviour. [10]

The aggressively invasive behaviour had led many researchers to suggest that it might be a benign neoplasm rather than a simple cyst and various investigative studies were carried to identify the molecular characteristics that supported this hypothesis.

The reasons that were thought suggested an aggressive behaviour and provided supportive evidence that the OKC was a benign neoplasm as summarized from the reports by Shear are as follows:

1. Expansive growth patterns thought to be due to mural growths and infoldings in the form of epithelial proliferation,
2. A higher mitotic rate of the cystic lining similar to an ameloblastoma, with a much higher mean than other cysts,
3. Presence of numerous growth promoting factors,
4. PCNA, Ki67 and p53 positivity seen more frequently and intensely in the OKCs, especially the syndrome associated cysts.,
5. Mutation of PTCH gene leading to the loss of this tumour suppressor gene,
6. The 'two-hits' hypothesis to support the argument of differences in syndromic versus sporadic occurrence,
7. Presence of keratin 16, Ki67 and a more intense staining with epithelial growth factor receptor (EGFr) leading to the conclusion that the OKCs had an intrinsic growth potential not present

in other odontogenic cysts.[11-13]

The period between the second edition to the the change of the millennium did not see any major changes in the terminology, however discussion about its aggressive behaviour and the potential of placing this cyst into the category of odontogenic tumours had begun to gain popularity gradually.

The name Keratocystoma was provocatively used by Shear, Keratocystic Odontogenic tumour was suggested by Philepsen and then Reichart and Philipsen in their book on Odontogenic tumours and allied lesions, reclassified odontogenic tumors and renamed OKC as Keratinizing Cystic Odontogenic Tumour (KCOT) and placed it under the subcategory of "Benign neoplasm of odontogenic epithelium with mature, fibrous stroma; odontogenic ectomesenchyme not present.[14, 15]

The third edition of 2005 WHO classification saw some major and controversial changes from the previous two editions of the

Table 3- WHO histological classification of Odontogenic Tumours, 3rd edition,2005.17

Malignant Tumours

Odontogenic Carcinomas

Metastasizing(malignant) ameloblastoma
Ameloblastic carcinoma- primary type
Ameloblastic carcinoma- secondary type (dedifferentiated), intraosseous
Ameloblastic carcinoma- secondary type (dedifferentiated), peripheral
Primary intraosseous squamous cell carcinoma- solid type
Primary intraosseous squamous cell carcinoma derived from keratocysticodontogenictumour
Primary intraosseous squamous cell carcinoma derived from odontogenic cysts
Clear cell odontogenic carcinoma
Ghost cell odontogenic carcinoma

Odontogenic Sarcomas

Ameloblasticfibrosarcoma
Ameloblasticfibrodentino and fibro-odontosarcoma

Benign Tumours

Odontogenic epithelium with mature, fibrous stroma without odontogenic ectomesenchyme

Ameloblastoma, solid/multicystic type
Ameloblastoma, extraosseous/peripheral type
Ameloblastoma, desmoplastic type
Ameloblastoma, unicystic type
Squamous odontogenictumour
Calcifying epithelial odontogenictumour
Adenomatoidodontogenictumour
Keratocysticodontogenictumour

Odontogenic epithelium with odontogenic ectomesenchyme with or without hard tissue formation

Ameloblastic fibroma
Ameloblasticfibrodentinoma
Ameloblastic fibro-odontoma
Odontoma
Odontoma, complex type
Odontoma, compound type
Odontoameloblastoma
Calcifying cystic odontogenictumour
Dentinogenic ghost cell tumour

Mesenchyme and/or odontogenicectomesenchyme with or without odontogenic epithelium

Odontogenic fibroma
Odontogenicmyxoma/myxofibroma
Cementoblastoma

Bone related tumours

Ossifying fibroma
Fibrous dysplasia
Osseous dysplasia
Central giant cell lesion (granuloma)
Cherubism
Aneurysmal bone cyst
Simple bone cyst

Other Tumours

Melanotic neuro ectodermal tumour of infancy

Table 4: WHO classification of odontogenic tumors and cysts, 4th edition, 2017. 21**Malignant Odontogenic Tumors**

Ameloblastic Carcinoma
 Primary Intraosseous Carcinoma, NOS
 Sclerosing Odontogenic Carcinoma
 Clear Cell Odontogenic Carcinoma
 Ghost Cell Odontogenic Carcinoma
 Odontogenic Carcinosarcoma
 Odontogenic Sarcomas

Benign Odontogenic Tumors**Epithelial Origin**

Ameloblastoma,
 Ameloblastoma, Conventional
 Ameloblastoma, Unicystic Type
 Ameloblastoma, Extrasosseous/ Peripheral Type
 Metastasizing (Malignant) Ameloblastoma
 Squamous Odontogenic Tumor
 Calcifying Epithelial Odontogenic Tumor
 Adenomatoid Odontogenic Tumor

Mixed (Epithelial-Mesenchymal) Origin

Ameloblastic Fibroma
 Primordial Odontogenic Tumor
 Odontoma
 Compound Type
 Complex type
 Dentinogenic ghost cell tumor

Mesenchymal Origin

Odontogenic fibroma
 Odontogenic myxoma/myxofibroma
 Cementoblastoma
 Cemento-ossifying fibroma

Odontogenic Cysts**Developmental Origin**

Dentigerous cyst
 Odontogenic keratocyst
 lateral periodontal and botryoid odontogenic cyst
 Gingival cyst
 Glandular odontogenic cyst
 Calcifying odontogenic cyst
 Orthokeratinized odontogenic cyst

Inflammatory Origin

radicular cyst
 Collateral inflammatory cyst

WHO classification, in that it excluded odontogenic cysts from this category and reclassified some cysts into neoplasms. One of the major changes of this classification was that Odontogenic Keratocyst (OKC) was reclassified as a neoplasm and recommended the term Keratocystic Odontogenic Tumor (KOT) as an appropriate designation (Table 3). [16, 17]

This classification got approval by WHO/IARC at the Editorial and Consensus Conference, held at Lyon, France in July 2003 and in 2005, WHO in their blue book 'Pathology and Genetics of Head and Neck Tumours', renamed OKC as "Keratocystic odontogenic Tumor" (KOT). It was then defined as "a benign uni- or multicystic, intraosseous tumour of odontogenic origin, with a characteristic lining of parakeratinized stratified squamous epithelium and potential for aggressive, infiltrative behaviour."

In justification of the reclassification, the WHO working group emphasized that this change was necessitated due to its aggressive behaviour, higher recurrence rate, occasional occurrence of a solid variant and mutations in the PTCH gene. [17, 18]

A reverse path from being a benign tumour to a cyst again.

Wright et al, stated in their paper that they personally did not find sufficient evidence to justify reclassifying OKC as a neoplasm. They explained with example that though fibrous dysplasia occurs due to a GNAS 1 mutation it cannot be reclassified as a neoplasm. They also quoted that most of the mutations were associated with syndromic patients and not otherwise. They argued that most major general pathology texts state that a neoplasm continues to grow, even if the stimulus which produced it is removed and neo-

plasms do not resolve spontaneously. In contrast to this OKCs have been well documented to resolve with decompression, that may result in the loss of the characteristic histologic features and even loss of PTCH exon 1b expression after decompression. Furthermore, the authors stated that even orthokeratinized odontogenic cysts and dentigerous cysts sometimes contain PTCH mutations and all these findings are against this cyst being classified as a tumour. They added that though in future we may reach a point where neoplasms can be defined at the molecular level, but we are not there yet, and they believe reclassifying OKCs as neoplastic was premature. Therefore they recommended that we revert to the previous terminology of odontogenic keratocyst. [16]

The 2017 WHO consensus group agreed that at the present time there was not enough evidence to support a neoplastic origin for the keratocyst and decided that the name of this lesion should revert back to Odontogenic Keratocyst and it should be classified as a developmental cyst. [19]

Kennedy too, in his paper stated that odontogenic cysts were a notable omission in the 3rd edition, which caused difficulties because there was an overlap between the histological appearances of odontogenic cysts and neoplasms. He added that this led to confusion, and the nomenclature was not widely accepted. He wrote that the propensity for recurrence, together with association with mutations of the Drosophila segment polarity gene Patched (PTCH) gene, had been taken as supportive evidence of a neoplastic designation. However, not all OKC possessed identifiable PTCH mutations and it was not clear whether the neoplastic designation was meant to apply to all OKC or only a subset. He further emphasized that the 2017 WHO panel did not think there was sufficient evidence to justify its classification as a neoplasm, and the designations OKC was back (Table 4) as the preferred term, though the 2005 term remains an acceptable synonym. [20, 21]

Conclusion

Odontogenic Keratocyst as we call it today has seen numerous changes and controversies in its journey, sometimes it was the origin that was debated, at other times it was its clinically aggressive behaviour, sometimes the molecular markers that supported its not so indolent nature and all this led to the numerous scientist, academicians and students discussing time and again, this cyst that we are so fond of and familiar today. These discussions have only widened our understanding of the histogenesis and the biological behaviour of this cyst. We hope that the better understanding and consensus help us identify this lesion as being a cyst with an aggressive behaviour like many other cysts, will lead to universally accepted treatment and management protocols. Also with so much change in terminologies it is the responsibility of

each one of us to use the term “Odontogenic Keratocyst” unambiguously so that further confusion in the literature is avoided.

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